

SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF FUTURE PHYSICAL TRAINING TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, the main terms encountered in the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical training teacher, the correct organization of pedagogical activity, the future of physical training teachers in the course of scientific pedagogical activity aspects to be considered and what approach is needed, as well as the organization of innovative and technological activities of the future physical education teacher.*

Keywords: *Physical education, pedagogical activity, pedagogical skills, innovative activity of the future physical training teacher, creativity, technological approach.*

One of the priority areas of our country's policy is the upbringing of a generation that is both physically and spiritually healthy. After all, today, in the context of the intensifying globalization processes in the countries of the world, raising a highly spiritual and physically well-developed generation is one of the most important factors determining the future of our Motherland and realizing the noble goals of our people. The legal basis for this noble cause has been created, and extensive work is being done. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. PQ-3031 dated June 3, 2017 "On measures to develop physical education and mass sports" and the Decree No. PF-5368 dated March 5, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" are of particular importance in the further development of this area. One of the main goals of these decrees and resolutions is to further deepen theoretical and practical knowledge in this area, to correctly form concepts and terms related to physical education skills and qualifications.

Indeed, in an era when globalization processes are becoming increasingly intense, the attention paid to physical education teachers who are directly involved in the general and special physical training of young people is gaining importance in this regard. After all, one of their important services is to direct students to such professions as educational, cultural, medical, industrial construction, and production, and secondly, to a certain extent, it serves to equip them with special physical training.

Today, teachers who educate the younger generation are required to fully master modern innovative technologies, have the skills to rationally use information and communication tools, and in general, be aware of all the secrets of education.

When studying issues related to the scientific and pedagogical activities of future physical education teachers, it is first of all appropriate to analyze the content and essence of the concepts related to this phenomenon. In particular, we can see that the concept of "physical education" itself has been given several definitions. "Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the morphological and functional aspects of the human body, the formation

and improvement of basic movement skills, abilities, and knowledge related to them that are important for its life".

Definitions such as "Physical education is education and physical exercises aimed at comprehensively strengthening the body, aimed at strengthening health" have been given.

In various fields, whether he is a mathematician, physicist, historian or physical education teacher, his work style is directly related to pedagogical activity. The meaningful and high-quality conduct of the lesson, in turn, is closely related to his pedagogical skills, pedagogical abilities, pedagogical qualifications, and pedagogical activity in general. The famous Russian pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky expressed his definition of pedagogical activity as follows: "One of the secrets of pedagogical leadership is to arouse in teachers an interest in systematic research and analysis of their own work. Whoever tries to distinguish between good and bad in their lessons, in their interactions with their students, and to share their achievements and shortcomings in a timely manner, will have achieved half the success of pedagogical activity". From this point of view, a young future physical education teacher who has just begun his pedagogical career cannot completely relax physically and mentally or completely surrender to peace. As we know, this feeling is called "relaxation" in psychology and is recognized as an assessment of negative situations in people's work.

In order for each future physical education teacher to fully master pedagogical skills:
firstly, to have mastered his subject based on the requirements of the era;
secondly, to have psychological and pedagogical knowledge (to be able to use methods appropriate to the character of students);
thirdly, to develop pedagogical curiosity and dedication in himself.

Russian scientist I.P.Rachenko expresses the following opinion about pedagogical skills as a part of pedagogical art: "Pedagogical skills are understood as a teacher's perfect mastery of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, professional qualifications and skills, interest in his profession, developed pedagogical thinking and intuition, moral and aesthetic attitude to life, confidence in his own opinion and firm will".

Also, the most important components of the pedagogical activity of a future physical education teacher are loyalty to the teaching profession, perfect knowledge of the methodology

of teaching his subject, ability to demonstrate pedagogical abilities, and ability to apply pedagogical techniques in their place.

It should be noted that each future physical education teacher, along with delivering physical exercises to students, is always engaged in their education and upbringing, and communicates with them. Since each student is constantly developing mentally, spiritually and physically, the future teacher must be in constant communication with them, take into account each of their psychological characteristics and physiological characteristics, thoroughly study the mechanisms of influence, first of all, the theory of psychology and education, and constantly develop his professional activity.

In this regard, we believe that future physical education teachers should pay special attention to the following during their scientific and pedagogical activities:

- have a perfect mastery of the system of knowledge about physical education;
- have the skills and qualifications to fully deliver physical exercises to students;
- knowledge of the basics of general methodological sciences, in particular, current issues of state policy, in addition to mastering their subject;
- ability to independently analyze social problems and processes occurring around them from their own point of view;
- gaining knowledge about the spiritual image of students during the educational process;
- ability to apply modern pedagogical and psychological knowledge, based on the age characteristics of students;
- ability to independently master, improve and use the newly acquired knowledge on a scientific basis in their work;
- ability to individually use regulatory legal documents in their scientific and pedagogical activities;
- adherence to the culture of communication;
- ability to analyze the acquired knowledge based on a critical approach;
- ability to clearly convey the acquired knowledge to students;
- formation of a sense of responsibility for their profession;
- to have mastered one of the foreign languages during the pedagogical activity as a means of professional qualification or scientific communication;
- to be able to effectively use modern information technologies;
- to be able to use modern pedagogical technologies in pedagogical activity, etc.

Also, future physical education teachers must have a perfect knowledge of the physical culture terms used in their pedagogical activities. Of course, the clear, precise and appropriate use of terms by the teacher directly affects the quality of the student's physical training. Indeed, each of us uses physical culture terms widely in our daily lives today. We can meet and encounter them in almost all subjects available in educational institutions. It should be noted that "today there are more than 15 thousand concepts and terms specific to about 300 sports existing in the world".

Future physical education teachers should be able to speak deeply, effectively, logically, beautifully in their pedagogical work with students and be able to use educationally significant phrases in their place. It should not be forgotten that the teacher's speech is a source of

inspiration for each student, and should not be rude, insulting, humiliating, or attacking a student who is even carelessly angering him or her and violating discipline, but should have the ability to get out of the situation in a positive way. When the teacher conducts a lesson, his or her voice should be a tool for controlling the audience. When explaining exercises related to physical education, he or she should be able to raise and lower his or her voice at the right place to indicate what the students should focus on.

Based on the above analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

firstly, the ongoing comprehensive reforms require not only the training of personnel in various fields, but also the fundamental improvement of the scientific and pedagogical activities of personnel in the field of physical education in educational institutions;

secondly, the analysis of issues related to the scientific and pedagogical activities of future physical education teachers shows that, despite the availability of views and sources on the subject, this issue should be studied from a purely pedagogical perspective;

thirdly, it is appropriate for a future physical education teacher to create the necessary conditions for the thorough assimilation of knowledge during his scientific and pedagogical activities, taking into account the interests, abilities and requirements of students, rationally using modern achievements of science and pedagogical technologies;

Fourthly, the era itself shows the need for future physical education teachers to effectively use such unique approaches as creativity, innovation, and technology, which play an important role in their scientific and pedagogical activities;

Fifthly, any teacher should set a goal to develop pure-minded, courageous, sociable, determined, spiritually and physically mature individuals during the lessons. This, in turn, will be the basis for the formation of qualified personnel who will serve the development of our country in the future.

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